

THE EFFECT OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE ON JOB SATISFACTION MEDIATED BY JOB STRESS

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Abstract

This study aims to examine and explain the effect of work-life balance on job satisfaction mediated by job stress at Bali Mutia Car Rental. This research adopts a quantitative associative design involving 62 respondents selected through a saturated sampling method. Data collection was conducted using questionnaires, and the analysis was performed using inferential techniques, specifically SEM-PLS (Structural Equation Modeling–Partial Least Squares) with SmartPLS 4.0 software. The findings reveal that work-life balance negatively influences job stress while positively affecting job satisfaction. Furthermore, job stress has a negative impact on job satisfaction and serves as a mediating variable in the relationship between work-life balance and job satisfaction. These results are consistent with role theory, which suggests that imbalances in roles may lead to role conflict, thereby disrupting work-life balance and increasing job stress. Elevated levels of stress, in turn, contribute to a decline in employee job satisfaction. This research is expected to offer practical insights for organizations in enhancing employee job satisfaction by managing work-life balance and job stress effectively.

Keywords: Work-Life Balance; Job Stress; Job Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Companies depend on support from various parties, including human resources, to achieve their objectives (Muktamar et al., 2024). The quality of human resources is a crucial factor in organizational success in today's competitive era (Purnama et al., 2020). Companies conduct recruitment and selection processes according to the best standards to obtain qualified employees capable of performing assigned tasks (Kristanto et al., 2024). Organizations have the responsibility to maintain various factors that support the workforce to ensure optimal contributions (Oktafianingsih & Suharini, 2024).

Bali Mutia Car Rental is a transportation service company operating commercially and plays an important role in supporting the tourism sector in Bali. The company provides safe, comfortable, and high-quality car rental services for both tourists and local communities. Its operations are influenced by several factors, such as the number of customers, service demand, vehicle fleet condition, and service quality. Bali Mutia Car Rental is committed to delivering the best service by prioritizing customer satisfaction, comfort, and safety. Achieving organizational goals requires professional and high-quality human resources to support operational performance and maintain customer loyalty.

The researcher conducted observations and interviews at Bali Mutia Car Rental and identified job dissatisfaction among employees. Employees reported frequently

being assigned tasks or contacted outside working hours. It was also found that employees lack effective communication with supervisors and that relationships among coworkers are less harmonious.

Job satisfaction refers to the positive feelings employees experience toward their work and working conditions (Anees et al., 2021). Individuals are considered satisfied when they feel content and pleased in performing their jobs (Wahyuni & Dewi, 2024). The level of job satisfaction is influenced by how well job activities align with individual expectations (Dhani & Surya, 2023). Employees who feel satisfied tend to show higher levels of engagement in carrying out their duties and responsibilities (Memon et al., 2023).

According to Linton (1936, p.114), role theory views individual behavior in society as influenced by the roles they occupy, where each individual performs rights and obligations based on their position within a social structure. Role theory explains how individuals perform specific roles to maintain social stability (Inayah & Puryandani, 2022). A role set refers to a collection of roles held simultaneously by an individual (Putri et al., 2023). Role conflict has a significant negative effect on employee job satisfaction (Rashida, 2021). A supportive environment can reduce role conflict and ultimately increase job satisfaction (Badewin et al., 2023). Role conflict or role ambiguity can trigger job stress and reduce job satisfaction (Dwipayana & Suwandana, 2024). Individuals with good work-life balance are more effective in managing and integrating their roles (Aura & Hutahaean, 2024).

Job stress is a condition experienced by individuals when faced with job demands that exceed their ability to cope (Maghfirah, 2023). It arises from both internal and external factors (Pratiwi et al., 2024). Poorly managed job stress can negatively affect employees' mental and physical health and reduce service quality (Joshi et al., 2023).

Work-life balance refers to how employees balance their professional and personal lives, as well as how workplace policies and practices support them in achieving this balance (Bintang et al., 2024). It is one of the factors influencing job satisfaction (Abhinandan, 2021). Employees who successfully balance work and personal life tend to be more satisfied with their jobs (Rondonuwu et al., 2018), while imbalance leads to decreased job satisfaction (Rachmawati & Susanto, 2024).

Previous studies (Humaini et al., 2023; Sari & Hasyim, 2022; Damayanti & Atmaja, 2022; Rizan et al., 2022) consistently show that work-life balance improves job satisfaction. However, research gaps exist, as some studies (Endeka et al., 2020; Permatasari & Sugiarto, 2024; Herlina et al., 2025) found no significant relationship between work-life balance and job satisfaction.

This research is intended to deepen understanding regarding the influence of work-life balance on job satisfaction, with job stress functioning as a mediating variable. The findings are expected to help organizations improve employee job satisfaction by enhancing work-life balance.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses an associative quantitative approach to analyze the relationship between work-life balance as the exogenous variable, job satisfaction as the endogenous variable, and job stress as the mediating variable. The research was conducted at Bali Mutia Car Rental located in Seminyak, Badung, Bali, with the research object focusing on employees' job satisfaction, job stress, and work-life balance.

Job satisfaction was measured using indicators of work, salary, promotion, supervision, and coworkers. Job stress was measured through task demands, role demands, and interpersonal relationships. Work-life balance was assessed based on the balance between personal life and work, including both positive and negative interactions (Robbins & Judge, 2008; Wahyuni & Dewi, 2024; Samallo & Wulani, 2022; Kusuma & Ali, 2024; Septian et al., 2024; Mahadiva, 2022).

The population consisted of 62 employees, using a saturated sampling technique in which all members of the population were selected as respondents, with the criterion of contract employees who had worked for more than six months. The data included quantitative data in the form of questionnaire scores and respondent characteristics, as well as qualitative data describing the company profile.

Primary data were obtained through questionnaire distribution, while secondary data were derived from company documents. Data collection employed a survey method using closed-ended questionnaires based on a Likert scale (1–5), which had been tested for validity (correlation coefficient ≥ 0.3) and reliability using Cronbach's alpha (> 0.6) (Sugiyono, 2018; Sugiyono, 2019; Alfreh et al., 2021).

Data analysis techniques included descriptive and inferential statistical analysis using Structural Equation Modeling–Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) with SmartPLS software. The analysis involved two main models: the outer model (to test validity and reliability through convergent validity, average variance extracted, discriminant validity, and composite reliability) and the inner model (to examine relationships between latent variables using path coefficients, R^2 , and Q^2). Hypothesis testing was conducted using the t-test based on t-statistics and p-values (< 0.05) to determine the significance of relationships between variables (Ghozali & Kusumadewi, 2023; Nurhalizah et al., 2024; Sugiyono, 2018).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Characteristics

Table 1. Respondent Characteristics

No	Characteristics	Classification	Total (Persons)	Percentage (%)
1	Length of Service	7–12 Months	27	43.6
		13–24 Months	24	38.7
		>24 Months	11	17.7
		Total	62	100
2	Age	20–25 Years	30	48.4
		26–30 Years	28	45.2
		>30 Years	4	6.4

No	Characteristics	Classification	Total (Persons)	Percentage (%)
		Total	62	100

Source: Processed data (2026)

The majority of respondents have a tenure of 7–12 months, indicating the dominance of relatively new employees in line with the company’s business expansion. Based on age, employees are predominantly in the 20–30-year range, representing a productive age group with high mobility and work flexibility. In terms of gender and marital status, respondents are mostly male and unmarried, which aligns with job demands requiring field activities and flexible working schedules.

Description of Research Variables

Table 2. Variable Description Criteria

Average Score	Job Satisfaction	Job Stress	Work-Life Balance
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low	Very Low	Very Low
1.81 – 2.60	Low	Low	Low
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
3.41 – 4.20	High	High	High
4.21 – 5.00	Very High	Very High	Very High

Source: Processed by the author

Respondents’ perceptions indicate that employee job satisfaction at Bali Mutia Car Rental falls within the moderate category, with an average score of 2.95, suggesting that conditions are not yet optimal and still require improvement. The lowest score is found in the aspect of enjoyment at work, while the highest score reflects that supervisors have performed adequately in providing direction.

Job stress is also categorized as moderate, with an average score of 3.29, indicating that stress levels remain within a reasonable range but need to be monitored as they approach the upper threshold. Meanwhile, work-life balance has an average score of 2.91 (moderate category), with the main challenge being personal time management, although work still has a positive impact on employees’ personal lives.

Results of Inferential Analysis Using PLS (Partial Least Squares) Method
Figure 1. Results of the PLS Algorithm Method

Outer Model Evaluation

The outer model is used to evaluate the relationship between indicators and latent variables in terms of validity and reliability. It determines whether indicators are formative (forming the latent variable) or reflective (influenced by the latent variable).

1) Convergent Validity Test

Table 3. Outer Loadings Test Results

Indicator	Variable	Outer Loadings	Description
Y1	Job Satisfaction	0.851	Valid
Y2	Job Satisfaction	0.829	Valid
Y3	Job Satisfaction	0.801	Valid
Y4	Job Satisfaction	0.806	Valid
Y5	Job Satisfaction	0.714	Valid
Y6	Job Satisfaction	0.739	Valid
Y7	Job Satisfaction	0.823	Valid
Y8	Job Satisfaction	0.843	Valid
Y9	Job Satisfaction	0.815	Valid
M1	Job Stress	0.824	Valid
M2	Job Stress	0.862	Valid
M3	Job Stress	0.824	Valid
M4	Job Stress	0.730	Valid
X1	Work-Life Balance	0.869	Valid
X2	Work-Life Balance	0.896	Valid
X3	Work-Life Balance	0.890	Valid
X4	Work-Life Balance	0.879	Valid

Source: Processed data (2026)

Referring to Table 3, the results of the convergent validity test indicate that all indicators associated with job satisfaction, job stress, and work-life balance exhibit

outer loading values exceeding 0.70. This demonstrates that each indicator is valid and adequately represents its respective construct.

2) Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Test

Table 4. AVE Test Results

Research Variable	AVE
Job Satisfaction	0.646
Job Stress	0.659
Work-Life Balance	0.781

Source: Processed data (2026)

The AVE values for job satisfaction, job stress, and work-life balance are 0.646, 0.659, and 0.781, respectively. All variables have AVE values greater than 0.50, indicating that the research model is valid.

3) Discriminant Validity Test

Table 5. Cross Loading Discriminant Validity Test

Indicator	Job Satisfaction	Job Stress	Work-Life Balance
Y1	0.851	-0.629	0.654
Y2	0.829	-0.592	0.694
Y3	0.801	-0.640	0.656
Y4	0.806	-0.556	0.651
Y5	0.714	-0.565	0.532
Y6	0.739	-0.588	0.483
Y7	0.823	-0.628	0.586
Y8	0.843	-0.648	0.594
Y9	0.815	-0.565	0.546
M1	-0.635	0.824	-0.566
M2	-0.626	0.862	-0.482
M3	-0.645	0.824	-0.649
M4	-0.508	0.730	-0.403
X1	0.627	-0.481	0.869
X2	0.681	-0.647	0.896
X3	0.687	-0.630	0.890
X4	0.652	-0.553	0.879

Source: Processed data (2026)

4) Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha Test

Table 6. Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha Results

Variable	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha	Description
Job Satisfaction	0.942	0.931	Reliable
Job Stress	0.885	0.827	Reliable
Work-Life Balance	0.934	0.907	Reliable

Source: Processed data (2026)

The results show that all research variables have values above 0.70. Job satisfaction has a composite reliability of 0.942 and Cronbach's alpha of 0.931. Job stress has values of 0.885 and 0.827, respectively, while work-life balance has values of 0.934 and 0.907. These results indicate that all variables demonstrate good reliability.

Inner Model Evaluation

1) Table 7. R-square Test Results

Table 7. R-square Test Results

Variable	R Square
Job Stress	0.433
Job Satisfaction	0.678

Source: Processed data (2026)

The R-square value for the job stress variable is 0.433, which implies that 43.3% of the variation in job stress can be explained by work-life balance, while the remaining 56.7% is attributed to other factors not included in the model.

Similarly, the R-square value for job satisfaction is 0.678, indicating that 67.8% of its variance is explained by work-life balance and job stress, whereas 32.2% is influenced by variables outside the model.

2) Predictive Relevance Test (Q-square / Q²)

The predictive relevance of the model was evaluated using the Q² value, which assesses the model's ability to reconstruct observed data based on its parameter estimates. A Q² value greater than 0 (Q² > 0) signifies that the model has adequate predictive relevance, while a value less than or equal to 0 (Q² ≤ 0) indicate otherwise.

The Q² calculation is as follows:

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - R1^2) (1 - R2^2)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - 0,433) (1 - 0,678)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (0,567) (0,322) = 1 - 0,182574 = 0,817426$$

The Q² value of 0.817 indicates that the research model has strong predictive relevance since it is greater than 0. This value implies that 81.7% of the variance in job satisfaction can be explained both directly and indirectly by work-life balance and job stress within the proposed model, while the remaining 18.3% is influenced by external variables not examined in this study.

Hypothesis Testing

**Table 8. Hypothesis Testing Results
Direct Effects**

Hypothesis	Original Sample	t-statistic	P-values	Description
Work-Life Balance (X) → Job Stress (M)	-0.658	9.392	0.000	Significant
Work-Life Balance (X) → Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.454	5.296	0.000	Significant

Hypothesis	Original Sample	t-statistic	P-values	Description
Job Stress (M) → Job Satisfaction (Y)	-0.450	5.069	0.000	Significant

Indirect Effects

Hypothesis	Original Sample	t-statistic	P-values	Description
Work-Life Balance (X) → Job Stress (M) → Job Satisfaction (Y)	0.297	4.640	0.000	Significant

Source: Processed data (2026)

Interpretation of Hypothesis Testing

1. Effect of Work-Life Balance on Job Stress

The original sample value is -0.658, with a p-value of 0.000 (< 0.05) and a t-statistic of 9.392 (> 1.96). These results indicate that work-life balance has a significant negative effect on job stress. This means that higher levels of work-life balance experienced by employees lead to lower levels of job stress. Thus, the first hypothesis is accepted.

2. Effect of Work-Life Balance on Job Satisfaction

The original sample value is 0.454, with a p-value of 0.000 (< 0.05) and a t-statistic of 5.296 (> 1.96). These results indicate that work-life balance has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction. This implies that better work-life balance leads to higher employee job satisfaction. Therefore, the second hypothesis is accepted.

3. Effect of Job Stress on Job Satisfaction

The original sample value is -0.450, with a p-value of 0.000 (< 0.05) and a t-statistic of 5.069 (> 1.96). These findings indicate that job stress has a significant negative effect on job satisfaction. This means that higher job stress reduces employee job satisfaction. Thus, the third hypothesis is accepted.

4. Mediating Effect of Job Stress

The mediation test examines the indirect effect of work-life balance on job satisfaction through job stress. The results show an original sample value of 0.297, with a p-value of 0.000 (< 0.05) and a t-statistic of 4.640 (> 1.96), indicating a significant indirect effect.

Since the direct effect of work-life balance on job satisfaction is also significant, job stress functions as a partial mediator in the relationship between work-life balance and job satisfaction. Therefore, the fourth hypothesis is accepted.

Discussion

The Effect of Work-Life Balance on Job Stress at Bali Mutia Car Rental

The results of this study confirm that work-life balance has a negative effect on job stress among employees at Bali Mutia Car Rental, indicating that better perceived balance leads to lower levels of stress. These findings are consistent with Role Theory, which explains that individuals perform multiple roles, each requiring the fulfillment of certain rights and obligations.

In this study, interference between work roles and personal life creates imbalance, indicating that employees fail to achieve work-life balance, which in turn increases job stress. These findings are consistent with previous studies by Malik and Verma (2025), Pramesti and Adnyani (2025), Salwa et al. (2025), Singh and Juneja (2025), Putri and Satrya (2025), Prasad et al. (2025), Riantika et al. (2024), Maharani and Tamara (2024), Paramita and Supartha (2022), and Aoerora and Marpaung (2020), all of which conclude that work-life balance has a significant negative effect on job stress.

The Effect of Work-Life Balance on Job Satisfaction at Bali Mutia Car Rental

The results show that work-life balance positively influences job satisfaction at Bali Mutia Car Rental. This means that the better the work-life balance experienced by employees, the higher their level of job satisfaction. These results are also aligned with Role Theory.

In this context, work interference with personal life and the decline of personal life due to work reflect an imbalance, which ultimately reduces job satisfaction. These findings are supported by prior research conducted by Erlinda and Sawitri (2025), Septian et al. (2024), Nugroho (2025), Izharuddin (2024), Bintang et al. (2024), Firdaus et al. (2024), Dwipa and Dahmiri (2023), Damayanti and Atmaja (2022), Susanto et al. (2022), and Silaban and Margaretha (2021), which state that work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

The Effect of Job Stress on Job Satisfaction at Bali Mutia Car Rental

The study demonstrates that job stress negatively affects job satisfaction, meaning that higher levels of stress tend to reduce employees' satisfaction levels. These findings are consistent with Role Theory.

A mismatch between assigned tasks and job descriptions can lead to role conflict and role ambiguity, which may trigger job stress and ultimately reduce job satisfaction. These results are in line with studies by Erlinda and Sawitri (2025), Lin et al. (2024), Attamimi (2024), Maharani and Tamara (2024), Kusuma and Ali (2024), Nuraeni and Gunawan (2022), Rizan et al. (2022), Mardikaningsih and Sinambela (2022), Puspitawati and Atmaja (2021), and Xie et al. (2021), which also found a significant negative relationship between job stress and job satisfaction.

The Effect of Work-Life Balance on Job Satisfaction Mediated by Job Stress at Bali Mutia Car Rental

This study demonstrates that job stress mediates the relationship between work-life balance and job satisfaction among employees at Bali Mutia Car Rental. The higher the level of work-life balance perceived by employees, the lower their job stress, which in turn enhances job satisfaction.

These findings are consistent with Role Theory, which explains that individuals perform multiple roles with specific demands and limitations. Imbalance due to poor work-life balance can trigger role conflict, increasing job stress. Elevated job stress subsequently reduces job satisfaction.

These results are supported by previous studies conducted by Safitri and Suratman (2026), Malek et al. (2025), Aulia and Putra (2024), Muzti and Mardiana (2024),

Jessica et al. (2023), Aviola et al. (2022), Nuraeni and Gunawan (2022), Aruldoss et al. (2022), Abhinandan (2021), and Aoerora and Marpaung (2020), which indicate that work-life balance influences job satisfaction through job stress as a mediating variable.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions can be drawn:

1. Work-life balance has a negative effect on employee job stress at Bali Mutia Car Rental. This indicates that better work-life balance leads to lower levels of job stress among employees.
2. Work-life balance has a positive effect on employee job satisfaction at Bali Mutia Car Rental. This means that better work-life balance results in higher job satisfaction among employees.
3. Job stress has a negative effect on employee job satisfaction at Bali Mutia Car Rental. This indicates that higher job stress leads to lower job satisfaction.
4. Job stress functions as a mediating variable in the relationship between work-life balance and job satisfaction at Bali Mutia Car Rental. This means that improved work-life balance reduces job stress, which in turn enhances job satisfaction among employees.

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